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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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EXPLORING PROTECTIONS AVAILABLE TO MINORITY MEMBERS UNDER NIGERIAN CORPORATE LAW

By

Dr. Shamsuddeen Magaji,* Abubakar Garba Salisu**

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ABSTRACT

In managing the affairs of a company, the majority members have a very significant influence on the business operations of the company in recognition of the corporate majority principle established in *Foss v Harbottle* (1843) 2 Hare 461. Majority members always maintain that the company affairs be conducted in a manner most favourable to them even if the actions are detrimental to the minority shareholders. This leads to a question of how minority shareholders are being protected under Nigerian corporate law. The objective of this study is to explore the protection accorded to minority shareholders under the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA 2020) and to understand whether these protections are enforceable. The study employed both doctrinal and non-doctrinal methods (socio-legal) to answer the research questions and achieve the objectives. Interviews were conducted with 15 respondents across the states of Bauchi, Kano, Abuja, and Lagos with relevant stakeholders. The findings in the study indicate that, although provisions were made under the CAMA 2020 protecting minority members, particularly members' direct action, derivative action and relief on the ground of unfairly prejudicial or oppressive conduct, investigation of the affairs of the company and petition for winding up. Yet, minority members are still being oppressed due to procedural requirements before exercising these protections, lack of awareness of how members could exercise their rights and in some instances the delay in justice administration in Nigeria. It is recommended that shareholder associations should be at the forefront of educating shareholders about the remedies available and how to exercise these remedies. It is equally recommended that CAMA 2020 should have a clear definition of what amounts to oppressive or unfairly prejudicial conduct to limit wide discretionary interpretations by the courts. Finally, the Chief Judge of the Federal High Court should issue a practice direction that would fast-track cases of minority members to strengthen corporate democracy and good governance.

Keywords: Derivative action, majority members, minority members, minority protection, remedies

1. INTRODUCTION

There are two basic organs of a company which are the management (board of directors) and members of the company at general meeting.¹ Based on the fact that, it is hard for all the shareholders² to run the activities of the company, the board is in a fiduciary position to act in the best interest of the company as a whole.³ Directors are under obligation to safeguard the interest of all shareholders and to act in achieving maximum benefit.⁴ The board is equally accountable to members at the company's general meetings.⁵ Shareholders' stake in a particular company determines majority shareholders and minority shareholders.⁶ This is the basis through which majority shareholders can influence the decision of a company and therefore minority shareholders need protection from majority shareholders against detrimental actions.⁷ The protection is necessary to ensure that majority shareholders would not abuse the principle of majority rule. Otherwise, it would compromise corporate governance and accountability, which in the end make corporations lose investments from minorities.⁸ Furthermore, it means

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¹ Shamsudeen, Magaji, "Improving Member's Participation in the Annual General Meeting under Nigerian Corporate Law," PhD Thesis, School of Law, Universiti Utara Malaysia (2018); Eze J.A. Organs of the Company that affect Corporate Wider Responsibility: A review. *Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Journal of Commercial and Property Law* (2021) Oct 8;3(1).

² In this study shareholders and members are used interchangeably through technically the research is referring to members whose name are registered and have all membership rights.

³ Moore Colin R., "Obligations in the shade: The Application of Fiduciary Directors' Duties to Shadow Directors," *Legal Studies* 36, no. 2 (2016): 326-353.

⁴ Kala Anandarajah, *Corporate Governance, A Practical Approach* (Asia, Butterworth: 2001), 15-16.

⁵ Croci Ettore and Ettore Croci, *The Board of Directors*. Springer International Publishing (2018); *John Shaw & Sons (Salford) Ltd v Shaw (1935) 2 KB 113*.

⁶ Olayinka Adenikinju, Folasade Ayonrinde, Adeola Adenikinju, Analysis of ownership structure in Nigeria quoted companies and its correlation with corporate performance, *African Journal of Economic Policy* Vol. 10(2) 2003: 57-80

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸ Azu, E. U, Examination of Recent Trends in Corporate Governance as it Affects the Majority Rule and Minority Protection, *International Journal of Advanced Legal Studies and Governance*, Vol. 1 No. 1, (April, 2010) 81. http://www.icidr.org/ijalsg_vol1no1_april2010/Examination%20of%20Recent%20Trends%20in%20Corporate%20Governance%20as%20it%20affects%20the%20Majority%20Rule%20and%20the%20Minority%20Protection. (accessed April 14, 2023).

shareholders (members) having more than a simple majority of voting rights have veto powers to determine the fate of a resolution.⁹

Minority shareholders could only institute an action where the conduct of majority shareholders is illegal or *ultra vires* against their personal rights provided by statutes.¹⁰ Though, minority shareholders exist, their opinions could not be heard, even when it comes to voting. Thus, the rights of minority shareholders are at the mercy of majority shareholders¹¹. However, recent developments in corporate governance have helped immensely in mitigating the frustrations posed to the minority, by providing them with certain rights and remedies to the extent that they could sue the company, even though the majority may have a contrary opinion.¹² Majority shareholders on the other hand, have the right to ratify any irregularity done to the company. This resulted to serious problems for minority shareholders, as the courts in many cases have been reluctant to intervene in favour of minority members.¹³

In Nigeria, there are protections accorded to minority shareholders against oppression by majority shareholders.¹⁴ This is because where the minority shareholders could not be protected against oppressive conduct, that would make corporate participants to lose hope in investing their resources in companies and the potential shareholders may also lose their confidence. In other words, failure to protect minority shareholders has a detrimental effect to corporate existence in general.¹⁵ The majority rule has negatively affected minority shareholders, in that they only have the right to attend and vote at company meetings, but their opinions would not bind the company where majority members are against such opinion. This means that, minority shareholders are at the whims of majority shareholders. In one aspect, the principle has impacted in reducing the multiplicity of cases against a

⁹ Andrew Hicks & S.H. Goo, *Cases & Materials on Company Law*, 6th Edition (New York, Oxford University Press: 2008) 429.

¹⁰ Art Robert C., "Shareholder Rights and Remedies in Close Corporations: Oppression, Fiduciary Duties, and Reasonable Expectations." *J. Corp. L.* 28 (2002): 371.

¹¹ Cory Jacques, "The Inefficient Safeguards of the Minority Shareholders," *Business Ethics: The Ethical Revolution of Minority Shareholders* (2005): 7-19; Ogunlade Femi Z., "The Imperative of Shareholders Participation in Promoting Corporate Governance: Minority Protection and Majority Rule in Focus," *Journal of Commercial and Property Law* 10.2 (2023): 116-132.

¹² Solomon Dov, "The Voice: The Minority Shareholder's Perspective," *Nev. LJ* 17 (2016): 739.

¹³ Shamsuddeen Magaji, *Protection of Minority Shareholder under Nigerian Company Law*, unpublished LLM Dissertation, School of Law, Universiti Utara Malaysia, 2015.

¹⁴ *S.H.O Williams (Junior) & Anor v J. Olabode Williams (1995) LPELR- 3483 (S. C)*.

¹⁵ Simon Ejembi, *Protecting Minority Shareholders*. The Punch Newspaper, Nigeria, August 12, 2013. <http://www.punchng.com/business/money/protecting-minority-shareholders/> (accessed December 25, 2023)

company, by empowering only the company the right to seek redress for wrongful act.¹⁶ On the other side, this appeared to affect minority members as the courts are unenthusiastic to interfere with the (internal management) of the company.¹⁷

The issue of minority shareholders' protection has been given great significance globally due to the misuse of corporate powers as decided in many celebrated cases; including Enron scandal¹⁸ in the USA. Enron was incorporated in the year 1985 in the USA. It was amongst the leading electricity, communications and natural gas company in the world, until its bankruptcy and fall in the year 2001 mainly due to lack of duty of good faith and disclosure by the company's management.¹⁹ The company was fraudulently involved in misrepresenting their earnings when the management embezzled the company's assets which caused the investors subsequently to suffer financial loss.²⁰ In Australia for example, the court in the case of *WCP Limited v Gambotto & Anor*²¹ has stressed that although the court recognized the right of majority shareholders to decide the fate of their company; they must not at the same time oppress minority members.

In Nigeria, one of the famous cases of corporate mismanagement was that of *Bata Nig Plc*.²² The company was a leading manufacturer in leather and textile industry. The company had a good prospect in business but in 1997, Chief (Mrs.) Olakunri, Chairman of the Board of Directors willfully caused one of its major stockholders; Bata Overseas Trading Company (BOTC), which owned 40% shares to exit from the company. She then transferred all the shares to herself and family members without the consent and approval of the shareholders. She equally used their shares as collateral and secured loan to pay the number of shares left by BOTC. The company never made any disclosure for such transactions.

¹⁶ Aderibigbe, O. I, Corporate Litigation and the Majority Rule: Retreating from the Precipe, *International Journal of Advanced Legal Studies and Governance*, Vol. 3 No. 3, (December, 2012) 36. http://www.icidr.org/ijalsg_vol3no3-dec2012/Corporate%20of%Litigation%20And%20The%20Majority%20 (accessed November 24, 2023).

¹⁷ *Edokpolo & Co Ltd v Sem Edo Wire Ind. Ltd. & Anor (1984) LPELR 1017 (S.C)*.

¹⁸ *235 F. Supp. 2d 549, 2002 U.S*

¹⁹ Elson, Charles M., and Christopher J. Gyves. "The Enron failure and corporate governance reform." *Wake Forest L. Rev.* 38 (2003): 855.

²⁰ <http://finance.laws.com/enron-scandal-summary>. (accessed March 15, 2024)

²¹ (1993) 11 ACLC 457 (*New South Wales Court of Appeal*). Mitchell, Vanessa "Gambotto and the Rights of Minority Shareholders," *Bond Law Review*: Vol. 6: Iss. 2, Article 1(1994). <http://epublications.bond.edu.au/blr/vol6/iss2/1>

²² How Bata Company was Mismanaged. <http://www.nairaland.com/2080837/how-bata-shoe-company-mismanaged> (accessed April 30, 2023).

All the above cases established the necessity of protecting minority members and its relevance in corporate management.²³ There is the need to regularly examine the protections accorded to minority shareholders so that workable recommendations can be suggested, to ensure investment in corporations are more accountable and attractive. It is equally believed that there are a lot of reasons that would facilitate Foreign Direct Investments to Nigeria, involving flexible legal and regulatory frameworks.²⁴ It is also believed that the protection of shareholders particularly through Portfolio Investment would make Nigerian corporations more attractive.²⁵ This is because, effective corporate management may persuade investors to invest in various companies in Nigeria.

The objectives of this study is to identify the protections accorded to minority shareholders in Nigeria under CAMA 2020; and to examine the adequacy of the remedies available to minority shareholders and their enforceability.

2. BRIEF LITERATURE REVIEW

A brief literature review covering general discussion of this study is presented here. The CAMA 2020 as the primary legislation regulating companies in Nigeria provides some remedies to minority shareholders. One cannot discuss the principle of majority rule without reference to the case of *Foss v. Harbottle* which empowers a company as the only proper party/plaintiff to seek redress or institute an action for any wrong or liability incurred by the company. An individual or minority member cannot sue or take action to redress the wrong or irregular conduct on behalf of the company.²⁶ This principle also known as majority rule and was codified under section 299 of CAMA 1990 and now section 341 CAMA 2020 which repealed the 1990 Act. The position was emphasized in *Njemanze v. Shell B.P. Port Harcourt*²⁷ to the effect that; “*Once incorporated, the company and it alone must act and be acted against to enter into and apply its rights and obligations... Accordingly, an individual member of the company is precluded from appropriating to himself the right of action which belongs to the company*”. Similarly, the court

²³ Om ankhanlen Alex Ehimare, Taiwo Niyam Joseph, Okorie Uche; the Role of Corporate Governance in the Growth of Nigerian Banks, *Journal of Business Law and Ethics*, Vol. 1 No. 1, December 2013. www.aripd.org/jble (accessed April 5, 2024).

²⁴ Aderonke Adejugbe, Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria; Overcoming Legal and Regulatory Challenges to Foreign Direct Investments in Nigeria: is the Nigerian Government Doing Enough? May 1, 2013. http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2354319

²⁵ An Appraisal of Foreign Investment Promotion and Protection Measures Operating In Nigeria, *The Journal of World Investment & Trade*, Volume 3, Issue 2, (2002) 345 – 368. DOI: 10.1163/221190002X00148.

²⁶ *Gombe v. P.W. (Nig.) Ltd (1995) 6 NWLR (pt 404 402 SC; Ejikeme v. Amaechi (1998) 3 NWLR (pt 542) 456 C.A.; Daily Times (Nig) plc v. Akindiji (1998) 13 NWLR (pt 580) 22 at 27 CA. and N.I.B. Invest. West Africa v. omissore (2006) 4 NWLR (pt 969) 122 C.A.*

²⁷ (1966) AllNLR 8.

in *Alhaji M. U. Gombe v P. W. (Nigeria) Limited & Ors*²⁸ held that the company is the proper party to maintain an action unless where there is fraud.

In *Vassile v. Paas Industries Ltd*²⁹ the court held that, “A limited liability company is a juristic person and can sue and be sued in its corporate name. It is separate and distinct from shareholders, and directors. As such, it will be unnecessary to join any of its members or officers in an action against it (as Co-Defendant)”. In *New Resources Int'l Ltd & Anor v Ejike Oranusi Esq*,³⁰ the court made a similar pronouncement with the above case, but went further to add that, “No member of a company has a right to unilaterally commit the company on any matter without its consent and approval.”³¹

The above decisions indicate the importance of shareholders in determining the future of company's business. However, minority shareholders are susceptible to abuse by the majority hence the need to protect them. It is imperative at this juncture to cite the provision of section 341 of CAMA 2020 and the exceptions thereto which are part of the protections available to the minority shareholders. The section 341 provides:

“Subject to the provisions of this Act, where an irregularity is made in the course of a company's affairs or any wrong is done to the company, only the company can sue to remedy that wrong and only the company can ratify the irregular conduct.”

Again, section 341 further provides:

“Without prejudice to the rights of members under sections 346 to 351 and sections 353 to 355 of this Act or any other provisions of this Act, the court on the application of any member, may by injunction or declaration restrain the company from the following:

- (a) entering into any transaction which is illegal or *ultravires*;
- (b) purporting to do by ordinary resolution any act which by its constitution or the Act requires to be done by special resolution;
- (c) any act or omission affecting the applicant's individual rights as a member;

²⁸ (1995) LPELR 1330 (S. C).

²⁹ (2000) 12 NWLR (pt 681) 357.

³⁰ (2010) LPERP 4592 C.A.

³¹ (2010) LPERP 4592 C.A.

- (d) committing fraud on either the company or the minority shareholders where the directors fail to take appropriate action to redress the wrong done;
- (e) where a company meeting cannot be called in time to be of practical use in redressing a wrong done to the company or to minority shareholders; and,
- (f) where the directors are likely benefit, or have profited or negligence or from their breach of duty.”

The above provision is the basis of protection accorded to minority shareholders under the CAMA 2020. The section also laid down the process or procedure to be followed to enforce the protections available to minority shareholders. This is called members’ direct action which is part of the remedies available to minority members.

Furthermore, section 346 of CAMA 2020 provides for remedy of derivative action which include specific procedure to be followed in order to file a derivative action. This includes; notice to the management; the powers of court and other stipulated conditions. On the one hand, sections 353-354 CAMA 2020 empowered a member who allege oppressive conduct in the affairs of the company to file action by way of petition for relief against unfair and oppressive conduct. Though, this protection is not exclusively reserved for minority shareholders, the protection is also available to directors of the company, creditors, the Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) and any person which the court considers eligible. However, whether this remedy protects minority shareholders shall be examined later.

The court in *S.H.O Williams (Junior) & Anor v J. Olabode Williams*,³² considers the condition precedent in order to protect minority shareholders, namely; there must be oppressive conduct on minority shareholders. This is a ground upon which the court may exercise its discretion to wound up the affairs of a company. Oppressive conduct in this case has been defined to mean “*burdensome, harsh and wrongful act*”. Having laid the above background, the next headings would discuss on the various protections available to minority members, methodology, data analysis obtained through face-to-face interview then findings, recommendations, conclusion and recommendation for further research.

3. PERSONAL AND REPRESENTATIVE ACTION

³² supra note 24.

By the provision of section 344 CAMA 2020 a member may bring personal action for violation of his personal right and may bring a representative action for himself and on behalf of others. This protection is not exclusive for the minority shareholders. However, minority shareholders who feel their personal right(s) have been infringed may exercise this protection. The reliefs accorded to minority members are mostly in form of injunction or declaration, minority shareholders are not entitled to damages as a result of an act or omission of the majority.³³

4. DERIVATIVE ACTION

Section 346 CAMA 2020 provides that, “An applicant may apply to the Court for leave to bring an action in the name or on behalf of a company or a company’s subsidiary, or to intervene in an action to which the company or the company’s subsidiary is a party, for the purpose of prosecuting, defending or discontinuing the action on behalf of the company or the company’s subsidiary.” This similar provision under CAMA 1990 was judicially recognized in *Agip (Nig.) Ltd v Agip Petroli Int’l*³⁴ where the court held that the above conditions must be satisfied in order for the court to grant leave to the applicant. In the same case, the court held that derivative action as a remedy can only be resorted to by shareholders when leave of court has been obtained. Leave is granted by court where there is fraud; infringement of duty which members cannot ratify by ordinary resolution or where the management acted outside their powers. Though the court can grant leave to file action by way of derivative action, the problem has been how much fact is required before the court can grant leave to file such action, and even where leave is granted; it would not serve the utmost interest of minority shareholders. The Supreme Court described derivative action as, “shareholder derivative suit; brought by shareholder on behalf of a company against a third party. Often, the third party is an insider of the corporation, such as the directors or executive officers.” The main purpose of seeking leave to commence derivative action is to enable the court to first consider the application, to scrutinize all the documents in support of the application, to carry out an exhaustive review of the grounds for bringing the application and ensure that a *prima facie* case has been established before the directors are invited to oppose the application or the action itself.

³³ Ezekiel Chigozie, Corporate Sovereignty Under Nigerian Law, 2013. <http://wingrass.blogspot.com/2013/01/corporate-sovereignty-under-nigerian-law.html> (accessed May 7, 2023).

³⁴ (2010) 5 NWLR (Pt 1187) 225-428.

Thus, derivative action as a remedy for minority shareholders is justified based on the fact that where each shareholder is permitted to maintain an action against a company, the company would be overburdened with cases that may affect the business of the company; that the company felt “*that it might be killed by kindness*”.³⁵

Derivative action according to Kunle Aina is a procedure whereby minority shareholders seek redress in a court. It has been established that the Common Law provisions relating to derivative action has become a hurdle which prevents minority shareholders from resorting to it as a protection. The repealed CAMA 1990 in order to ease such difficulties faced by minority shareholders made provisions under section 303-309 based on recommendation of the Nigerian Law Reform Commission.³⁶ For example, section 350 of CAMA 2020 provides that no applicant for derivative action shall be asked to deposit security for cost. This would at least encourage minority shareholders to exercise their right. However, even with that, the challenge persists.

5. RELIEF ON THE GROUNDS OF UNFAIRLY PREJUDICIAL AND OPPRESSIVE CONDUCT

There is no definition provided in CAMA 2020 for the term “oppressive conduct”. However, in the English case of *Scottish Cooperative Wholesale Society Ltd v. Meyer*³⁷ the court defined the term oppressive conduct as, “*burdensome, harsh and wrongful*”. The Supreme Court of Texas for example in *Ritchie v. Rupe*,³⁸ described oppressive conduct as, “when the majority or directors abuse their authority over the corporation with the intent to harm the interests of one or more of the shareholders, in a manner that does not conform with the honest exercise of their business judgment, and by doing so create a serious risk of harm to the corporation.” The above requirement laid down by the court is difficult to prove by minority shareholders. Though in the above case, the court favoured the respondent’s company by holding that the act of the company does not amount to oppressive conduct.³⁹ However, in *Aspek Pipe Co (Pty) Ltd v Mauerberger*⁴⁰, the term oppressive conduct means, “a

³⁵ *Prudential Assurance Co Ltd v Newman Industries Ltd (No 2) (1982) 1 Ch 204 at 210.*

³⁶ Kunle, *supra*.

³⁷ (1959) A.C. 324 H.L.

³⁸ (2014) Tex. LEXIS 500.

³⁹ Gerard G. Petch, Peter A. Stoke and John J. Bryon, *Ritchie v. Rupe: End of Minority Shareholder Oppression in Texas*, 2014. <http://www.nortonrosefulbright.com/knowledge/publications/117907/ritchie-v-rupe> (accessed May 11, 2023).

⁴⁰ (1968) 1 SA 517 at 525H-526E.

visible departure from the standards of fair dealing and a violation of fair play on which every shareholder who entrusts his money to a company is entitled to rely..."

The above meaning was used by the Nigerian court in the case of *Ogunade v Mobile Films (W. A) Ltd.*⁴¹ *per Karibi- White* where the court held, "the oppression or fraudulent conduct of the majority must be harsh, burdensome and wrongful...and must represent a consistent pattern of conduct internationally directed at the oppressed minority over a period of time...Thus, negligence in conducting the affairs of the company or lack of business ability or inefficiency will not be sufficient..."

In *Ephraim F. Faloughi v Haniels Williams & Ors*,⁴² it was held that oppressive conduct is determined based on a peculiar fact. Nevertheless, the conduct must be such that amounts to fraud on minority shareholders or a violation of the provision of company's constitution or abuse of powers by majority shareholders. This definition has occasioned to failure of many petitions; even in the United Kingdom where the Jenkins Committee recommended for wider definition of the term oppressive conduct, in such a way that determines degree of culpability required to satisfy legal requisite.⁴³

This equally prompted most of the Commonwealth countries to amend their company legislation with a view to have wider meaning of the term *oppressive conduct* to include "unfairly prejudicial conduct" so that more protection is given particularly to minority shareholders.⁴⁴

It is worthy to mention that both CAMA 2020 and judicial decisions did not set out specific conducts termed as oppressive or unfairly prejudicial against minority shareholders. Each case is determined according to its peculiar fact.⁴⁵ However, the following are presumed to be some of the instances that are oppressive and unfairly prejudicial conduct against minority shareholders: "(a). where the directors vote for themselves excessive emoluments and therefore deprived minority shareholders of any reasonable dividend;⁴⁶ (b) where the

⁴¹(1976) 2 FRCR 101.

⁴² (1978) 4 FRCR 31.

⁴³ Report of the Working Party on the Harmonisation of Company Law in the Carribean Community, (1979)134.

⁴⁴ Nigerian Law Reform Commission, (1991) at 187.

⁴⁵Legal Remedies for Oppressed Shareholders, an Overview of Section 205 Companies Act. <http://www.pearse-trust.ie/blog/bid/101205/Legal-Remedies-For-Oppressed-Shareholders-An-Overview-Of-Section-205> (accessed May 12, 2023).

⁴⁶ Yibakua David Amakiri, Company Democracy- Majority Interest versus Minority Protection: Brief Analysis of the Legal Protection against Corporate Oppression, 2013. <http://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=3&ved=0CC8QFjAC&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.nigerianlawtoday.com%2F2013%2F09%2Fcompany-democracy-majority->

board of directors deny registration for personal representatives of deceased members which disenfranchises them and forces them to sale their shares at low prices;⁴⁷ (c) where the directors refuse to recommend payment of non-cumulative preference dividend on the shares of the minority shareholder;⁴⁸ (d) exclusion of substantial shareholder from management without justification;⁴⁹ (e) unjustly over reaching majority shareholders at detriment of minorities”.⁵⁰

The protection against oppressive conduct is extended to act which may likely oppress the minority.⁵¹ Minority shareholders can file petition where company’s business or any related affairs has been or likely being conducted in a way that prejudiced interest of minority shareholders.⁵²

Section 353 CAMA 2020 specify persons that can file petition before the Federal High Court⁵³ in order to protect minority shareholder’s interest. They are (a) a member of the company; (b) a director or officer or former director or officer of the company; (c) a creditor; (d) the Commission; or (e) any other person who, in the discretion of the court, is the proper person to make an application under section 354 of CAMA 2020. Based on this provision, it is clear that this remedy is not for the minority alone as held in *Wilson v Okeke*⁵⁴ (supra). Directors⁵⁵ are equally empowered to petition for this remedy, yet, it is not practicable due to the fact that directors are the ones managing the company. In this regard, Omyekachi opined that the statutory protections available to minority shareholders

interest_9.html&ei=vUM3VeXrL4nHuASA5YHgAQ&usg=AFQjCNGpHhqIRZsKhsBxX5UvF3GaoBcT7A&bvm=bv.91071109,d.c2E (accessed May 8, 2022).

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

⁴⁸ Akanki E. O., "Reformulating the Law Against Oppression in Companies" (1990/1991) 13-15 JPPL 28.

⁴⁹ *Re London Society of Electronics Ltd* (1986) Ch. 211.

⁵⁰ *Alexander v. Automatic Telephone Co. Ltd* (1900) 2 Ch. 56.

⁵¹ *Grancy Property Ltd v Manala* [2013] ZASCA 57.

⁵² Roodt Inc, The Oppression Section of the Companies Act Provides The Most Important Statutory Protection of Shareholders' Rights, 2013.

<http://www.mondaq.com/x/276094/Shareholders/The+Oppression+Section+Of+The+Companies+Act+Provide+s+The+Most+Important+Statutory+Protection+Of+Shareholders+Rights> (accessed May 12, 2022).

⁵³ s. 251 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) as amended.

⁵⁴ Kunle Aina, Current Development in the Law on Derivative Action in Nigerian Company Law (2014) <http://www.academia.edu/7175946>.

⁵⁵ Jackwell Feris, Relief from Oppressive Conduct. <http://www.bbrieff.co.za/resources/articles/relief-from-oppressive-conduct> (accessed April 18, 2022).

should properly be exercised. These include oppressive conducts that are detrimental to the interest of these shareholders⁵⁶. This protection can be exercised by petition.⁵⁷

6. GROUNDS FOR SEEKING RELIEF

The reason for setting out grounds upon which a petition is founded is to prevent abuse by minority shareholders. Section 354(a) CAMA 2020 set out the grounds which depends on whether the application is made by a member, CAC or by a director, creditor or any other person the court considered as a proper person. This can be seen below:

i. By member of the company who alleges:

“(i) that the affairs of the company are being conducted in a manner that is oppressive or unfairly prejudicial to, or unfairly discriminatory against, a member or members, or in a manner that is in disregard of the interests of a member or the members as a whole; or

(ii) that an act or omission or a proposed act or omission, by or on behalf of the company or a resolution, or a proposed resolution, of a class of members, was or would be oppressive or unfairly prejudicial to, or unfairly discriminatory against, a member or was or would be in a manner which is in disregard of the interests of a member or the member as a whole”.⁵⁸

ii. By director, creditor or any other person the court considered as a proper person who alleges:

“(i) that the affairs of the company are being conducted in a manner oppressive or unfairly prejudicial to or discriminatory against or which is in a manner in disregard of the interests of that person,

(ii) that an act or omission, or a proposed act or omission was or would be oppressive or unfairly prejudicial to, or unfairly discriminatory against, or which is in a manner in disregard of the interests of that person”.⁵⁹

⁵⁶ Omyekachi W. Duru, *A Comment on the Content, Context and Condition of Class Rights under Nigeria Company Law*, 2012 <http://www.docstoc.com/myoffice/recommendations?docId=128846041&download=1> (accessed October 7, 2022).

⁵⁷ s. 355 CAMA 2020.

⁵⁸ s. 354(2) (a) CAMA 2020.

⁵⁹ s. 354(2) (b) CAMA 2020.

The apex court in *Williams v Williams*⁶⁰ held that, for a petitioner to succeed, he must show and prove prejudicial or oppressive act, otherwise the petition would fail. In the case of *S. H. O Williams (Junior) & Anor v. J. B Olabode Williams (supra)* the court held that, “*there must be a continuing cause of oppressive conduct for such a petition to succeed. The conduct must also be such as to be oppressive to the petitioner in his capacity as a member.*”

iii. By Corporate Affairs Commission

In a situation where it appears to the Commission in the exercise of its powers under the provisions of this act or any other enactment that –

“(i) the affairs of the company are being conducted in a manner that is oppressive or unfairly prejudicial to, or unfairly discriminatory against a member or members or in a manner which is in disregard of the public interest; or

(ii) any actual or proposed act or omission of the company (including an act or omission on its behalf) which was or would be oppressive, or unfairly prejudicial to, or unfairly discriminatory against a member or members in a manner which is in disregard of the public interests”⁶¹

6.1 Powers of the Court

This is provided under section 355(1) (2) (a)- (j) of the CAMA 2020. The court upon being satisfied with the petition, may order: (a) for winding up; (b) regulate the affairs of the company in future; (c) purchase shares of any member by other members of the company; (d) reduction of company’s capital; (e) institute, prosecute, defend or discontinue specific proceedings, or authorize a member or the company to institute, prosecute, defend or discontinue specific proceedings for and on behalf of the company; (f) varying or setting aside a transaction which the company is a party and to compensate the company or any other party to the transaction or contract; (g) investigation by CAC; (h) appointing a receiver or a receiver and manager of in respect of the company’s property; (i) restrain a

⁶⁰ *Williams v Williams (1995) 2 NWLR (Pt. 375) 1.*

⁶¹ s. 354 (2) (c) CAMA 2020.

person from engaging in specific conduct or doing a specific act; (j) directing a person to do a specific act or thing”.

It is necessary to point out that the order concerning winding up⁶² is not usually in the best interest of minority shareholders and the company,⁶³ because minority shareholders may not likely benefit when the company is wound up. Nonetheless, nothing prevents the court from making such order if evidence established to that effect.⁶⁴ In essence, the court ordered for winding up in *Hillam v Ample Source International*.⁶⁵ Section 356 CAMA 2020 provides the penalty for failure to comply which is an offence and liable to a penalty as may be determined by the Commission. There are other protections or remedies available to minority members like investigation of the affairs of a company and winding up which forms part of recommendation for future studies.

7. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts socio-legal research methodology to achieve the research objectives. However, some relevant materials are found in libraries, databases and other achieves. The other set of data involved qualitative interview with selected 15 respondents. This study seeks to examine and analyse facts; legal provisions; and principles systematically⁶⁶ at the same time exploring the opinions of relevant respondent in the field of study.

8. SOURCES OF DATA

Both primary and secondary data were used. Primary data used in this study is CAMA 2020 which provides the law in addition to the interviews conducted. The respondents were selected from the academia, shareholder activist, corporate regulators and practitioners. Secondly, the study uses decided cases to achieve the objectives of this study. The secondary data used include journals, articles and authored texts both in hard copy and obtained through online, to compliment the primary data to achieve the objectives,

⁶² Obozuwa Enikeozuwa, *Minorities Shareholders Rights in the Case of Oppression*. http://www.academia.edu/5887268/Minorities_Shareholders_Rights_in_the_Case_of_Oppression (accessed May 20, 2022).

⁶³ Akintunde Emiola, *Nigerian Company Law*, (Nigeria, Emiola Publishers: 2007) 468.

⁶⁴ Kate French and Amy Stewart, *Oppressed minority shareholders and appropriate relief - Is winding up a solvent company an extreme step?*, 2012. <http://www.holdingredlich.com/dispute-resolution-litigation/oppressed-minority-shareholders-and-appropriate-relief-is-winding-up-a-solvent-company-an-extreme-step> (accessed April 27, 2022).

⁶⁵ (No 2) [2012] FCAFC 73.

⁶⁶ Anwaul Yaqin, *Legal Research and Writing* (Malaysia, LexisNexis: 2007)

respectively. In analyzing the data, this study adopts both thematic and content analysis methods.

9. DATA ANALYSIS

9.1 RESPONDENTS' PERSPECTIVE

Fifteen respondents were interviewed in this study. The questions concern Respondents' views on whether or not the remedies or protections accorded to minority shareholders are adequate and easily enforceable. The respondents are unanimous that CAMA 2020 has made reasonable provisions protecting minority shareholders. The respondents maintained that; enforcement of the protections/remedies is not effective for various reasons.

According to Respondent 2, "we have reasonable provisions under our laws protecting minority shareholder interest but the problem has to do with lack of awareness on the part of shareholders on the available remedies to the minority shareholders. This is very critical because without the knowledge of the remedies, minority shareholders could not even think of exercising these rights.⁶⁷ Similar view was maintained by Respondent 3 and 4.⁶⁸

According to Respondents 6 & 11, derivative action is amongst the remedies accessible to minority shareholders which allows a shareholder to bring an action on behalf of a company as against the general provision that only a company can file an action to remedy a wrong. However, a party may only be granted an injunction or declaration but to monetary remedy or compensation.⁶⁹

On the one hand, Respondent 7 argued that, the remedy for unfairly prejudicial or oppressive conduct are provided under CAMA to protect minority shareholders against oppression from the majority shareholders but procedural stipulations like seeking leave of court and other requirements involved before shareholders seek protection from the court are quite difficult making the remedies unenforceable".⁷⁰ In a similar vein, Respondents 9, 10, and 13 argued that, lack of definition of what qualifies as oppressive conduct is not provided in the CAMA. It is for our court to

⁶⁷ Respondent 2 (Lecturer, Kano, Nigeria) 2024.

⁶⁸ Respondents 3 & 4 (Lecturer-shareholder activist, Bauchi, Nigeria) 2024.

⁶⁹ Respondents 6 & 11 (Legal Practitioners, Bauchi, Nigeria) 2024.

⁷⁰ Respondent 7 (Regulator, Abuja, Nigeria) 2024.

decide. In many legislations, you would find a section in the Act defining some terms or concepts and therefore giving no wide gap of interpretation by the court.⁷¹

In his view, Respondent 8 added that, “apart from the challenge that most of the minority shareholders are not aware of remedies available to them and the problem of procedural requirement, there is the challenge of delay in the quick dispensation of justice. Many cases linger in our courts for several years. Except for specific cases that are *sui generis* (time-bound) like election cases being handled within a specific period; cases involving enforcement of shareholder rights are not classified as *sui generis* and therefore experience the typical lengthy delays in our courts. This alone makes minority shareholders reluctant to enforce remedies available to them.⁷² Similar views were held by Respondent 1, 14 & 15.⁷³

The Respondents argued that shareholder activism is critical in this regard. It is through shareholder associations or unions that should take charge of educating shareholders about the rights and remedies available to them and how to enforce them. This would strengthen corporate democracy, accountability and corporate governance.

10. FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDTION(S)

From the discussion in this study, it is clear that several protections are available to minority shareholders under the CAMA 2020 including derivative action, remedy for oppressive and unfairly prejudicial conduct, investigation of company by the CAC and petition for winding up. However, the problem relates to the enforcement of the remedies. The opinion of the respondents interviewed further supports the literature consulted to the effect that remedies are available to minority shareholders but enforcement of the remedies remains a challenge. Lack of awareness on the part of minority shareholders, procedural stipulations, lack of definition of what amounts to oppressive or unfairly prejudicial conduct in the CAMA and delay in enforcing the remedies are what hinder the enforcement of the remedies. It is therefore suggested that shareholder associations and regulators should take the responsibility of educating members on the remedies available to them and how to enforce the remedies; the CAMA should equally be reviewed to accommodate the definition of

⁷¹ Respondents 9, 10 & 13 (Shareholder Activist, Abuja, Lagos, Nigeria) 2024.

⁷² Respondent 8 (Lecturer, Abuja, Nigeria) 2024.

⁷³ Respondents 1, 14 & 15 (Legal Practitioners, Kano, Nigeria) 2024.

certain terms like oppressive conduct and unfairly prejudicial conduct, this would limit wide discretionary powers of court in interpreting these two terms. Minority shareholders are only entitled to injunctions or declarations but not to any monetary remedy or compensation. There is the need for inclusion of compensation to minority shareholders whose cases succeeded or even cost incurred in prosecuting the case. On the delay in fast-tracking cases on minority shareholders; it is not peculiar to the enforcement of minority shareholder cases but a general problem in the country. However, to encourage minority shareholders to exercise their rights; a practice direction should be issued by the Chief Judge of the Federal High Court of Nigeria giving priority to cases of enforcement of minority shareholder remedies. This would further strengthen corporate democracy, transparency and good corporate governance. Although, this study is not trying to undermine the powers of majority shareholders due to their large stake in a given company but at least to give some sense of belonging to the minority shareholders which in the long run may make corporate investments very attractive.

11. RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Further research may look at other remedies aside from the remedy for derivative action and unfairly prejudicial and oppressive conduct like investigation of the affairs of the company and winding up. Similarly, further research may look at the role of shareholder associations in improving the exercise of minority shareholder remedies. Again, further research may look at availability of recent pronouncements of court in respect of the subject of study reason being, there could be availability of cases decided base on the recent CAMA 2020 in the future.

12. CONCLUSION

Corporate democracy as in normal democratic set-up recognizes both majority and minority shareholders' interest. While minority may have their say, majority will always have their way. This study explored some of the protections available to minority shareholders under the CAMA 2020 specifically, derivative action, relief on the grounds of oppressive and unfairly prejudicial conduct, personal and representative action and examined whether these protections are easily exercised by the minority shareholders. The findings in this study indicates that reasonable protections are accorded to minority shareholders under CAMA 2020 but shareholder

associations and regulators need to do more to ensure the exercise of these protections/remedies otherwise the remedies would only exist in the statutes.